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Research article

Methyltransferase Like 3 and Fat Mass and Obesity-Associated Protein Are Required for H7N9 Infection in Cell Culture

Ying Luo¹, Ying Sun², Hui Liu², Bo Peng², Weihua Wu², Xin Wang²,
Qing Zheng^{1*}, Shisong Fang^{2*}**Author affiliations**¹College of Pharmacy, Jinan University, Guangzhou, China²Shenzhen Center for Disease Control and Prevention, Shenzhen, China**Author contribution:**

Ying Luo, article writing, contributed towards data collection and analysis; Ying Sun, Investigation; Hui Liu, reference search; Bo Peng, Investigation; Weihua Wu, Formal analysis; Xin Wang, Investigation; Qing Zheng, article writing, Supervision; Shisong Fang; editing, proof reading and project administration.

Address reprint requests to

Qing Zheng

College of Pharmacy, Jinan University, Guangzhou, China

Email: tzhengq@jnu.edu.cn

Shi-song Fang

Shenzhen Center for Disease Control and Prevention, Shenzhen, China

Email: 1229346705@qq.com**Core tip:**

We showed that the m6A methyltransferase METTL3 and demethylase FTO are important factors in H7N9 replication. METTL3 was dramatically increased in H7N9 infected A549 cells. Knock-down of METTL3 or FTO led to decreased viral protein expression and replication.

Abstract:

Background METTL3 (methyltransferase like 3) and FTO (fat mass and obesity-associated protein) are critical for establishing and regulating the m6A (N6-methyladenosine) modification, but very little is known about the function of m6A in the immune system or its role in interactions within the host immune system.

Methods Western blotting experiment was used to check the expression of the host proteins related to m6A modification after H7N9 influenza virus infection. Immunofluorescence experiment was used to identify whether the subcellular localization of related proteins. Moreover, we knocked down and over express endogenous METTL3 or FTO in A549 cells, and then infected the cells with H7N9 to test whether methyltransferases or demethylases affect H7N9 replication.

Result We confirmed that the expression pattern of m6A proteins was altered during H7N9 infection. METTL3 and FTO were located in the nucleus, and YTHDF3 was located in the cytoplasm. Furthermore, our results demonstrate that downregulation of METTL3 or FTO expression in A549 cells severely impairs viral protein expression and H7N9 infection.

Conclusions METTL3 and FTO are critical for H7N9 replication which may represent a new mechanism for the control of H7N9 replication and host-pathogen interactions.

Key words METTL3, FTO; H7N9, RNA-seq.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 20 years, AIVs (avian influenza viruses), enzootic viruses, have posed a significant threat to public health and the poultry industry. Human infections with LPAIV (the low-pathogenic AIV) H7N9 were first reported in March 2013 in China ¹. The recent outbreak of H7N9 avian influenza in China was the fifth epidemic wave and raised major concerns worldwide ².

Influenza A viruses replicate in the nucleus and the genome is composed of eight RNA genome segments (vRNAs) of negative polarity. The RNA genome of an IAV comprises approximately 13,600 nucleotides encoding for up to 17 viral proteins ³. Although our understanding of the molecular mechanisms involved in the H7N9 infection of human cells has increased dramatically in the past few years, major determinants of H7N9 pathogenicity are still largely unknown. In particular, there is a large gap in our understanding of the genetic and epigenetic regulatory mechanisms that may govern the H7N9 life cycle and viral-host interactions.

m6A in RNA is a dynamic and reversible process. Adenosine methylation is catalyzed by a methyltransferase complex that contains METTL3, METTL14 and WTAP. Recently, it was shown that recombinant proteins were useful for mapping the binding surfaces within the METTL3-14-WTAP complex ⁴. m6A methylation can be reversed via active demethylation by two RNA demethylases, FTO and ALKBH5 ^{5,6}. Among m6A-binding proteins, the YTH N6-methyladenosine RNA-binding protein family members YTHDF1, YTHDF2, YTHDF3, YTHDC1, and YTHDC2, which are widely expressed in eukaryotes, have been the most well studied ⁷.

In the present study, we first investigated the change in m6A modification on viral RNA during H7N9 infection. We found that the expression of METTL3 and binding proteins was affected upon virus infection. Second, we attempted to comprehensively analyze the subcellular localization of METTL3, FTO and YTHDF3 proteins in the H7N9-infected A549 cells. Finally, we provide evidence that perturbation of the expression of m6A-related proteins altered viral replication, suggesting that the host m6A machinery is involved in viral replication. Taken together, our findings imply that METTL3 and FTO constitute an important process in the regulation of viral replication.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

ANTIBODIES AND REAGENTS USED

The A549 cell line, Madin-Darby canine kidney (MDCK) cell line, and H7N9 influenza virus were obtained from Shenzhen Center for Disease Control and Prevention (SZCDC). Antibodies against METTL3 and FTO were purchased from Abcam (Cambridge, MA, USA). The antibody against influenza A virus NP (nucleoprotein) was purchased from GeneTex (Irvine, CA, USA). The antibodies against β -actin and GAPDH were purchased from Santa Cruz (Santa Cruz, CA, USA). The secondary antibodies used in the study were goat anti-mouse and goat anti-rabbit, which were supplied by Thermo Fisher (Rockford, IL, USA).

Lipofectamine 2000 was purchased from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA). BCA kits, IP lysates were purchased from Beyotime. Cell culture medium DMEM (Gibco), Opti-MEM (Gibco), fetal bovine serum FBS (Gibco), TPCK-treated trypsin (Gibco) were obtained. Specific siRNA (sequences listed in **Table 1**) and pcDNA3.1 plasmid vector were synthesized by biosynthesis.

Table 1 The siRNA sequences used in this study.

siRNA	Sequences (5'-3')
Non-specific control	5'-UUCUCCGAACGUGUCACGUTT-3'
METTL3-1	5'-GCACUUGGAUCUACGGAAUTT-3'
METTL3-2	5'-GCUCAACAUACCCGUACUATT-3'
FTO-1	5'-ACACUUGGCCUCCUUUAUCUTT-3'
FTO-2	5'-GGCAAUCGAUACAGAAAGUTT-3'

CELL CULTURE AND VIRUS INFECTION

A549 and MDCK cells were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% or 5% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and incubated at 37°C under 5% CO₂, respectively. The cells were infected with H7N9 influenza virus at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 0.001 in independent biological triplicates and the cell culture supernatants included 0.25 µg/mL of trypsin. All experiments with H7N9 influenza virus were performed in enhanced biosafety level 3 (BSL3) containment laboratories at SZCDC.

PLASMIDS AND siRNA-MEDIATED GENE SILENCING

The pcDNA3.1 plasmid vector was used to overexpress METTL3 and FTO proteins in A549 cells. Specific METTL3 and FTO siRNAs were used to knockdown of METTL3 and FTO proteins in A549 cells. Both of them were transfected with Lipofectamine 2000 according to the manufacturer's protocol (reversible siRNA transfection method). Briefly, A549 cells (1.5×10^5) were transfected with specific siRNA (100 µM) or pcDNA3.1 plasmid vector (5 µg). At 6hr post-transfection, media were replaced. At 24hr post-transfection, the cells were infected with H7N9 viruses. The cells or supernatants were harvested at indicated time.

WESTERN BLOT ANALYSIS

Cells were seeded 1 day before infection and upon reaching 80% confluence were infected with H7N9 virus (MOI = 0.001). The cells were then harvested and lysed at the indicated times. The cell lysates were centrifuged and quantified, denatured by boiling in loading buffer for 12 min, and subjected to SDS polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). In brief, an equal amount of total protein was separated by SDS-PAGE and transferred to PVDF membranes (Millipore). The membrane was then incubated with the corresponding primary antibodies and secondary antibody. Immunodetection was performed using the Super Signal West Pico chemiluminescent substrate (Thermo Scientific) and scanned using Image Quant LAS 4000 (GE Healthcare).

IMMUNOFLUORESCENCE CONFOCAL MICROSCOPY

A549 cells were infected with H7N9 influenza virus for 24 h, and the cell monolayer was fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde. Then, Triton X-100 was used to permeabilize the cells, and 3% BSA was used to block the cells for 1 h. Rabbit anti-METTL3 and rabbit anti-FTO monoclonal antibodies were the primary antibodies used, Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-rabbit IgG was the secondary antibody used, and DAPI was used to stain with nuclei. After staining, the cells were washed with PBS and observed by laser confocal microscope.

IAV TCID₅₀ ASSAYS

The A549 cells transfected with siRNA and pcDNA3.1 plasmid in 6-well cell culture dishes were washed three times with PBS and infected with virus for 72 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Then, cell supernatants were obtained at 72 h after infection. The cell cultures were centrifuged at 5000 g for 1 min and the supernatants were stored at -80 °C. The viral titers in the supernatants were determined by 50% tissue culture infectious dose (TCID₅₀) in MDCK cells using the Reed-Muench formula⁸.

ETHICS STATEMENT

All procedures in this study were performed in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and the Helsinki declaration and were approved by the Medical Ethics Committee of Shenzhen Center for Disease Control and Prevention (SZCDC), Shenzhen, P. R. China.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

H7N9 INFECTION CHANGES THE EXPRESSION PATTERN OF M6a RELATED PROTEINS

To check whether H7N9 influenza virus infection affected the expression of the host proteins related to m6A modification, we analyzed H7N9-infected A549 cells by Western blotting using

antibodies against m6A-related proteins. The extent of the viral infection was monitored by NP expression. We found that, whereas the expression of the methyltransferase METTL3 was low under normal conditions, METTL3 expression increased 24 h postinfection (hpi). In contrast, the expression of the demethylase FTO was not changed after infection. The expression of the m6A-binding protein YTHDF3 increased 24 hpi (**Fig.1**). Together, these results show that the expression pattern of m6A proteins was altered during H7N9 infection.

Figure 1 (A) A549 cells infected with H7N9 (MOI=0.001) were harvested at indicated times post infection. Western blotting was performed with antibodies as indicated. (B) Relative intensity of METTL3. (C) Relative intensity of YTHDF3.

m6A RELATED PROTEINS ARE COLOCALIZED WITH THE NP VIRAL PROTEINS

Since the replication of negative single-stranded H7N9 influenza virus takes place in the nucleus and undergoes changes in m6A modification, we next examined the subcellular localization of METTL3, FTO and YTHDF3 proteins in the H7N9-infected A549 cells. Although there was no apparent redistribution of the enzymes upon H7N9 infection, the presence of METTL3 and FTO in the nucleus was confirmed by immunofluorescence staining of the H7N9-infected cells. YTHDF3 was located in the cytoplasm. Moreover, NPs were detected in the nucleus and cytoplasm (**Fig.2**). The colocalization of m6A-related proteins with the NP viral proteins implied that these proteins might interact with H7N9 viral RNA.

Figure 2 Confocal microscopy images of H7N9- or mock-infected A549 cells. The nucleus (blue) were labeled with DAPI. The METTL3, FTO, NP and YTHDF3 (green) were stained with antibodies as indicated, respectively. Scale bars, 5 μ m.

EXPRESSION OF METTL3 AND FTO REGULATE THE REPLICATION of H7N9

As the expression of endogenous methyltransferases or demethylases is known to affect HIV and EV71 protein expression and virus production, we knocked down endogenous METTL3 or FTO in A549 cells, and then infected the cells with H7N9 to test whether methyltransferases or

demethylases affect H7N9 replication. The viral titer was measured by TCID50, and the efficient knockdown of METTL3 resulted in a significant decrease in virus titer. Interestingly, the virus titer of H7N9 was also decreased when FTO was knocked down (**Fig.3E**). Similarly, the expression of NP was significantly decreased when either METTL3 or FTO was knocked down (**Fig.3A-D**). Consistent with the results of the knockdown experiments, we found that the viral titer was increased by METTL3 and FTO overexpression (**Fig.4**). Collectively, these results suggested that the m6A methyltransferase METTL3 and demethylase FTO profoundly influence efficient H7N9 replication.

Figure 3 (A and B) Western blotting. METTL3 and FTO were knocked down in A549 cell line by siRNA and then infected with H7N9. Western blot was carried out to check NP and confirm the knockdown efficiency of METTL3 and FTO. (C and D) Relative expression of NP. (E) viral titers level was tested by TCID50.

Figure 4 (A and B) Western blotting. METTL3 and FTO were overexpressed in A549 cells. Western blotting was carried out to check the expression of METTL3 and FTO. Vector-transfected cells were used as a control. (C) Viral titers (TCID50/ml) at 72 hr post-infection. A549 cells in which specific overexpression (OE) experiments was performed as indicated were infected by H7N9, and the supernatants were collected to measure virus titers as TCID50.

CONCLUSIONS

Here, we found that the expression of m6A-related proteins was altered by virus infection. METTL3, the key components of methyltransferases, together with YTHDF3 protein, were up-regulated. These data implied that H7N9 infection altered host proteins expression to enhance RNA m6A modifications, which may promote viral infection. Furthermore, both this methyltransferase and demethylase are present in the nucleus of A549 cells, while the YTH protein is located in the cytoplasm. Recent studies have shown that m6A-related proteins in the nucleus and cytoplasm regulate the viral replication process in host cells. Although H7N9 virus RNA replication and viral ribonucleo-proteins (vRNPs) assembly occur in the nucleus, vRNPs must be exported to the cytoplasm for assembly and germinate on the plasma membrane. It is necessary to study the effect of the YTH protein on virus replication in the cytoplasm.

Subsequently, we investigated the role of host METTL3 and FTO in H7N9-infected A549 cells. We found that the depletion and overexpression of METTL3 or FTO affects viral replication. Interestingly, both proteins act as negative regulators of the H7N9 virus. This result may be because of the changes to the levels of protein expression in the host upon H7N9 infection. In addition, METTL3 and FTO target different sets of transcripts of different biological processes in different cell types. METTL3 shows multifaceted functions that likely depend on its cellular localization and posttranslational modifications, and FTO can exhibit differential substrate preferences in the nucleus than it does in the cytoplasm. FTO can also regulate or recognize m6A in specific regions of a transcript, leading to different functional results. Overall, our study confirms the importance of METTL3 and FTO in the process of H7N9 replication.

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